

////////////////////////////////////

STUDY ON SEMIOSIS OF HUMAN BEHAVIORS AFFORDED BY ARCHITECTURE AND URBAN SPACE USING MULTIAGENT SYSTEM

Kumiko KISO* / Teruyuki MONNAI*

*Department of Architecture and Architectural Engineering,
Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan
hm.k-kumiko@archi.kyoto-u.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

The purposes of research are to show a way to analyze architectural/urban space and to consider a spatial design method. In architectural or urban space, there are infinite elements like people, buildings, trees, and so on. They interact constantly with each other and the composition is changing perpetually. So in this study, architectural/urban space is understood as a discrete system, where all the elements continuously interact and change in discrete time. The system is analyzed focusing on the human behavior, in order to understand the interrelation between people and architectural space. These 4 steps are followed;

- 1) Observation and description of human behaviors
- 2) Analysis of the description and extraction of main spatial behavioral rules
- 3) Spatial behavior modeling and simulations with Cellular Automaton based on the extracted rules
- 4) Consideration of a space design resulting from the comparison of the spatial characteristics of the simulated and the observed spaces.

Keywords: Human behavior, Cellular automaton, Architectural design

1. INTRODUCTION

Architectural/urban space is a discrete system composed of infinite elements including people, in which all the elements are constantly changing and interacting. This study shows a way to design this complex system, especially through the understanding of human behaviors.

The human behavior is understood to be a semiotic relation with human interpretations in this study. The human behavior shows how people understand

their surroundings, places, etc. If a person sits on a big stone, for example, it represents that he understands the stone as something to sit on. Semiosis is any human interpretation process. Semiosis of human behavior is therefore corresponding to any human interpretation process of his environment, and this idea is based on the semiotics theorized by Charles S. Peirce¹⁾. Through understanding semiosis of human behavior, we make out how the architectural/urban space speaks to people, how people speak to the space, and how to respond to them through spatial design.

2. OBSERVATION OF HUMAN BEHAVIORS IN AN ARCHITECTURAL SPACE

2-1 ABOUT THE SITE

Fig.1 Plan of the site

The campus square with a grand staircase and a pond in Seika University (Kyoto, JAPAN) is chosen to

observe human behaviors in a daily situation (fig.1, fig.2). We can see various human behaviors there, like eating, reading a book, and so on (fig.3).

Fig.2 The campus square with a grand staircase and a pond in Seika University

Fig.3 View from the point A in fig.1

2-2 OBSERVATION METHOD

The observation was done on 26th in July 2007 between 10h and 11h, 12h and 13h. The site was recorded by video and photos taken every 1 minute (fig.4). The weather condition is on table1. It was sunny during the observation and warm in the morning, hot in the afternoon.

Fig.4 Observation: view point is marked in fig.1

Table1 weather condition²⁾

average (°C)	temperature(°C)				humidity(%)		average wind verocity (m/s)
	max		min		average (%)	min (%)	
	°C	time	°C	time			
28.6	32.8	16:04	25.1	23:56	63	48	1.8

3. DESCRIPTION OF HUMAN BEHAVIORS

3-1 DEFINITION OF THE HUMAN BEHAVIOR

The action, the activity, and the human behavior are defined as below based on the definition by Hitoshi Watanabe³⁾.

a) Action

The action is the physical change of the part of the body (e.g. bend a finger, move eyes)

b) Activity

The activity is a group of actions, and is the physical change of the all of the body (e.g. eat, read a book)

c) Behavior

The behavior is a group of activities (e.g. eat while walking, talk while swimming).

Based on this definition, the human behavior is defined as a composition of human flows (which contains stops) and human activities during the flow.

3-2 DESCRIPTION OF HUMAN STOPS

Fig.5 Description of stop points (right:enlargement) a cell size is 25X 25 cm

Table2 Contents of the stops

ID	Number of time	Group size	with who	Start time	Finish time	Position	Activity1	Activity2
1	1	4	2,3,4	0:00	2:13	stand	talk	
2	1	4	1,3,4	0:00	1:23	stand	talk	
2	2	4	1,3,4	1:32	2:08	stand	talk	
3	1	4	1,2,4	0:00	1:36	stand	talk	
4	1	4	1,2,3	0:00	2:13	stand	talk	
5	1	2	6	0:00	0:40	stand	take pics	talk
5	2	1		1:20	1:32	sit	take pics	
5	3	1		1:36	1:51	sit	take pics	
5	4	1		1:54	2:19	stand	take pics	

Table3 Contents of human behaviors confirmed every 1 minutes photos and capture shots of the video

Fig.5 shows examples of the description. When the flows have stop points, detailed information is given such as coordinates (X, Y) of the point, stopping time, activities during the stop, type of stop (e.g. in a group or not), etc (table2, table3). The total number of stops is as below.

- 1) 10h - 11h: standing 10, sitting 75, other 1
 - 2) 12h - 13h: standing 41, sitting 117, other 3
- Fig.6 shows all the plotted stops.

Fig.6 All the plotted human stops: right 10:00-11:00, left 12:00-13:00

3-3 DESCRIPTION OF HUMAN FLOWS

Fig.7 Examples of description of human flows

Fig.8 All the plotted human flows: right 10:00-11:00, left 12:00-13:00

All the observed paths of the flows on video are traced on plans by hand (fig.7). Each path has its detailed information such as length, number of stops,

etc. Each path is distinguished by the person making it. The total number of flows is as below.

- 1) 10h - 11h: 270
- 2) 12h - 13h: 216 flows.

Fig.8 shows all the plotted flows.

4. ANALYSIS OF HUMAN BEHAVIORS AND EXTRACTION OF MAIN HUMAN BEHAVIORS

Main human behaviors are extracted as main human behavioral rules in the site from the description above. Peirce's semiotic category^{4),note1)} is used in order to focus on the multiplicity of human behavior.

4-1 CLASSIFY THE MAIN HUMAN BEHAVIORS ACCORDING TO PEIRCE'S CATEGORY

There are diverse human behaviors in architectural/urban space as there are various interpretations on the architectural elements. For example, a stone is understood as something beautiful for an artist, as something to sit for a tired person, and as something nostalgic for a person who habitually sees it from his childhood. Peirce's three categories, which can classify all the phenomena^{4),note1)}, are referenced to deal with this multiplicity of human interpretations. Following Peirce's idea of three categories, main observed human behaviors are classified into these three categories; 1) behavior from elements, 2) behavior from reaction between elements, and 3) behavior from structure of elements^{5),note2)}.

Table4 shows the examples of elements, relations between elements, and structure of elements.

1) BEHAVIORS FROM ELEMENTS

When a human behavior is affected by an architectural element itself, the behavior is extracted and is classified into this category based on firstness^{note1)}. When a human behavior is affected by the quality or property of element itself, the behavior categorized here.

2) BEHAVIORS FROM RELATIONS BETWEEN ELEMENTS

When a human behavior is affected by a relation between elements, not only by the element itself, the behavior is extracted and is classified into this category based on secondness^{note1)}. The relation cannot exist without elements.

3) BEHAVIORS FROM STRUCTURE OF ELEMENTS

When a human behavior is affected by a structure of elements, the structure is extracted and is classified into this category based on thirdness^{note1)}. The “structure” is, in this study, a particular arrangement or composition (especially habitual one) of relations.

Table4 Examples of Element, Relation, and Structure

Element	Relation between Elements	Structure of Elements
Quality or property of element (atmosphere, air, feel, etc.)	Quality or property of relation between elements (direction, disposition, height, physical effect etc.)	Quality or property of structure of elements (habitude, meaning, program, function, etc.)

5-2 EXTRACTION OF MAIN HUMAN BEHAVIOR RULES

Frequently observed human behaviors are extracted from the description as typical human behaviors in the site and are classified as below.

1) BEHAVIORS FROM ELEMENTS

(a) SIT CLOSE TO FRIENDS/SIT AWAY FROM OTHERS

Fig.9 Sitting beside friends, away from others

Table.5 Effects of friends upon stops

		10:00~11:00		12:00~13:00	
		single	with friends	single	with friends
all (sit, stand other)	total num	48	37	55	106
	sec/time	25.3	35.5	160.2	204.4
stand	total num	40	35	39	78
	sec/time	15.2	25.5	17.7	46.2
sit	total num	8	2	14	27
	sec/time	137.4	22.0	430.8	664.3

As we already know in the proxemics by Edward T. Hall⁽⁶⁾⁷⁾, more or less, friends sit close to each other and sit away from others in the site (fig.9). When people communicate each other, we judge that they are friends. Table4 shows effects of friends upon stops. According to table5, they sit longer than those who don't communicate (except 2 stops of 10:00-11:00 which are done with friends, not longer than that of single). They start to sit with friends right from the start or start to sit without friends at the beginning (fig.10).

The friend is a factor to attract his friend and also a

factor to lengthen the time to stop.

Fig.10 Above: Start to sit with friends right from the start (ID 32, 33 12:00-13:00) Below:Start to sit without friends at the beginning (ID 56, 58 12:00-13:00)

(b) SIT UNDER TREES

Fig.11 Frequency of stop (unit: time): right 10:00-11:00, left 10:00-11:00

Fig.12 Average span of stop (unit: sec/time): right 10:00-11:00, left 10:00-11:00

Fig.11 shows the frequency of the stops. Fig.12 shows the average time of the stops in each 100cm x

100cm cell. Both the frequency and the average span of stop are higher around the tree in the frame of dotted line in fig.11, fig.12.

Those who stay around trees tend to do many human behaviors (like eat, read a book, use a mobile phone etc.) after they start to stay (fig.13). This explains one of the reasons why they stay longer.

Fig.13 Activity sequence of those who stop around trees

Fig.14 Flows around the tree: left: flows whose exits are the same, right: flows whose exits are different

Fig.14 shows all the flows that have stops around the tree. According to fig.14, 3 persons who stop around the tree between 10:00-11:00 use 2 different exits to enter and go out of the site. On the other hand, except for these 3 persons, people who stop around the tree use the same exits to enter and go out from the site (fig.14). Each individual uses different exits depending on his position, but the process is the same; come to the site, stop at the tree, and go out of the site, and they don't stroll between their stopping points. If their purpose is to get to the exit quickly and efficiently, they will not pass around the tree. This explains that people come near the tree to stop and to pass time there.

Around the tree is fit for some behaviors like eating, reading a book etc. (fig.13); it's not comfortable to eat or read a book in the very center of a path, for example. The tree is thus a factor to attract people who want to do something which need the environmental quality of around trees, and as a result of the continuance of those human behaviors, the time to stop is lengthened.

2) BEHAVIORS FROM RELATIONS BETWEEN ELEMENTS

(a) SIT IN THE SHADOW OF TREES

Fig.15 shows the stopping points and the shade area of the site. Many people sit in the shade (fig.15). Table6 shows a relation between the shadow and stops. From Table5 especially between 12:00-13:00, when it is hot, people stay longer and more frequent in the shadow than those of 10:00-11:00.

That is to say, trees are also recognized to have a cooling effect to people. People who sit to avoid the heat take advantage of the physical effect of the shade made by trees and the sunlight.

Fig.15 Stop points and the shade: right 10:00-11:00, left 10:00-11:00

Table6 Stop and the shade

position	in/out of the shadow	10:00~11:00		12:00~13:00	
		in	out of	in	out of
all (sit, stand other)	total num	42	44	98	63
	sec/time	42.2	19.9	265.5	70.9
stand	total num	5	5	35	6
	sec/time	159	69.6	672.9	68.8
sit	total num	37	38	63	54
	sec/time	26.4	13.7	39.1	33.9

(b) SIT ON STARECASES WHICH HAS HIGH RISERS

Fig.16 and fig.17 show the relation between the stopping points and the positions during stopping. Almost all the stops "sitting" are done on staircases

(fig.16,17). In the site, the staircases can be divided into 2 types according to the height of riser. One has about 25 cm of risers, and the other has about 40 cm. The former's tread is wider than the latter (fig.2). The major stopping positions on the 40cm risers are "sitting" (28 stops of all the 40 stops on the 40cm risers are "sitting"), and the height of risers thus affords sitting positions. Table7 shows that average stopping span is longer on the higher risers. As conclusion, when we choose a place to stop, physical character of the environment is perceived, like the height of risers.

Fig. 16 Stop points and their positions between 10:00-11:00

Fig. 17 Stop points and their positions between 12:00-13:00

Table7 Stop postures, the total number of stops, the frequency of stops: data on the higher risers is shown in the parentheses.

	stand		sit	
	10:00~11:00	12:00~13:00	10:00~11:00	12:00~13:00
total num	75(3)	117(9)	10(6)	41(22)
sec/time	19.8(56.7)	36.6(380.7)	114.3(179.8)	584.5(830.5)

(c) AVOID WALKING FOR A LONG TIME

There are mainly 2 trees in the site (fig.2). Fig.18 shows all the flows coming to these 2 trees. When people stay around the tree, they choose the tree as

near from themselves as possible (from fig.18 and video). That is to say, when we choose a place to stop, physical character of the environment is perceived, like the distance from oneself.

Fig. 18 The flows coming to trees: left: come to the left tree right: come to the right tree

3) BEHAVIORS FROM STRUCTURE OF ELEMENTS

MEET FRIENDS: Many stops in the site (143 stops / 247 stops, about 58 %) are done with friends. It is because the site is the university where stopping to meet friends is frequent. Some habitude in the university (e.g. students come to the university, students have friends in their university) make the stops with friends frequent.

4) MULTIPLE BEHAVIORS AT THE SAME TIME

SIT AWAY FROM OTHERS / SIT IN THE SHADOW

Fig. 19 Stop around the same tree with that of fig.9 between 12:00-13:00

As shown in 1) BEHAVIOR FROM FEELING, people take some distance from others like in fig.9, but when it becomes hotter between 12:00 -13:00, the distance become shorter than that of between 10:00-11:00. Fig.19 is the photo of the same spot with that of fig.9, and in this spot 3 persons stop at the same time at the maximum between 10:00-11:00, but 10 persons stop at the same time at the peak between

12:00-13:00. People choose the inside of the shadow to avoid the heat, and at the same time people take some distance from others in the shade. In this case, the reactive aspects of the human behavior precede that of feeling. Thus people understand multiple meanings of the environment and each chooses the place to sit according to the environmental condition or his preference.

6. MODELING OF HUMAN BEHAVIOR AND SPACE/ MULTIAGENT-BASED SIMULATIONS WITH CELLULAR AUTOMATON

Based on the analysis, human behaviors are modeled and a simulator is made. The simulator is used to visualize interrelations between the human behavior and the environment in different situations.

6-1 MODELING OF THE EXTRACTED HUMAN BEHAVIORS

Human behaviors are simplified as below in order to make a behavioral simulator.

- 1) BEHAVIOR FROM ELEMENTS: people tend to stay beside friends or trees away from others.
- 2) BEHAVIOR FROM RELATION: people tend to stay in the shadow of trees, on the staircases whose height of risers is high, people choose environmental element to sit on as near from them as possible.
- 3) BEHAVIOR FROM STRUCTURE: people are students of the university, and they often see their friends there.
- 4) MULTIPLE BEHAVIORS: each person has each order of priority among friends, others and the shadow.

6-2 MODELING HUMAN BEHAVIORS WITH CELLULAR AUTOMATON⁸⁾ AND CREATE A SIMULATOR

1) MODELING WITH THE CELLULAR AUTOMATON (CA)

To model space and human behaviors at the same time, the Cellular Automaton (CA) is used. The CA is a general method for modeling a discrete system made up of local interrelations and is studied in physics, microstructure etc. The architectural phenomenon is also a discrete system in a sense, which consists of people, buildings and so on. The CA consists of a grid of cells. Each cell has a state that changes according to given rules. The procedure of modeling with the CA in this study is as below⁹⁾.

- 1) Simplify the study area by latticed cells
- 2) Give each state to each cell discretely
- 3) Make state transition rules which dictate every step to cells discretely
- 4) Let cells' states to change into another states according to the transition rules above

This procedure enables to model discrete transitions of all the architectural elements in space.

2) SIMPLIFY THE STUDY AREA AND SET CELLS IN THE SIMULATOR FOLLOWING THE SITE PLAN¹⁰⁾

First of all, the site is simplified by latticed cells. One cell size is 25cmx25cm and is from the width of the narrower tread; about 25cm. Following the site plan, cells are set, and each state is given to each cell according to the plan and the observation of the site; "person", "tree", "staircase" and "pond" are examples of the states (fig.20). Each cell has each coordinate (X, Y) and the location of the origin is at the corner of bottom-left (fig.20).

Fig.20 The simplified site and states of cells and the location of the origin

3) SET PERSON CELLS (AGENTS)

The cell whose state is "person" comes to stay in the site and is called in this study "agent".

In addition to the state "person", each agent has different variables as below.

ID; each agent has an "ID" to distinguish it from another agent.

Direction(fig.21); each agent look in each “direction”.
 Friend number; an agent is a friend of the agents whose “friend number” are the same mutually.
 Social distance⁶⁾⁷⁾ (fig.21); each agent read the states within this sphere.
 Personal distance⁶⁾⁷⁾ (fig.21); if 2 agents are friends mutually, the distance between 2 agents is less than “personal distance”, if not, the distance is more than “personal distance”.

Fig21. Right: “direction”, left: sphere of “personal distance” and “social distance”, and “direction”

4) MAKE INTERACTIVE TRANSITION RULES BETWEEN CELLS

Based on the analysis of human behaviors, state transition rules, are determined as below.

RULE1: BEHAVIORAL RULE AFEECTED BY ELEMENTS

- a) Friends and others: each agent has each “friend number”, and friends attract agents and they like to stay around their friends (fig.22)
- b) Trees: as well as friends, trees attract agents and they like to stay around trees (fig.22).

Fig.22 Part of the simulator: agents tend to stay around friends and trees

RULE2: BEHAVIORAL RULE AFEECTED BY RELATION BETWEEN ELEMENTS

- a) Shadow: as well as friends and trees, shadow attracts agents and agents like to stay in the shadow especially when it is hot (fig.23).

- b) Height of risers: agents like to sit on staircases whose risers are higher (fig.23).
- c) Distance: agents like to sit in a place as near from them as possible. The distance is calculated based on the coordinates of the cells (fig.24).

Fig.23 Part of the simulator: agents tend to sit on stair cases whose risers are higher, or around tree when hot

Fig.24 Distance between cells

RULE3: BEHAVIORAL RULE AFEECTED BY STRUCTURES OF ELEMENTS

All the agents are students of the university. So agents often see their friends in the university.

RULE3: MULTI-BEHAVORAL RULE

Order of priority: agents have their own order of priority about the choice of the place to stay. Order of priority is determined from order of these 3 conditions.

- Condition1: cells being within his friend’s “personal distance”.
- Condition2: “tree” cells
- Condition3: cells being out of other’s “personal distance”

Each agent chooses 1 cell to stay among the cells within his “social distance” according to his priority order.

Considering the rotation of the 3 conditions mentioned above, there are 6 types ($=_3P_3$) of priority order: 123,132,213,231,312,321.

Fig.25 diagrammatically shows this idea, which shows how the priority order “321” works, for example.

The agent whose priority order is “321”
 ; firstly choose among cells which satisfy all the 3
 conditions $3 \cap 2 \cap 1$
 ; when there are not cells satisfying $3 \cap 2 \cap 1$, choose
 among cells which satisfy $3 \cap 2$
 ; when there are not $3 \cap 2$, choose among cells which
 satisfy $3 \cap 1$
 Thus, agents take a place to stay step by step.

Fig.25 order of priority “321”

5) EXECUTION ORDER OF TRANSITION RULES

According to Interactive rules above, execution order of transition rules are determined. Fig.26 diagrammatically shows the order of agents’ transition rules as below.

Fig.26 Transitions rules of cells: left: before launch the simulator, right after launch the simulator: after launch the simulator, rules are circulated

STEP1) each agent takes his own states, variables and destination determined from his priority order)
 STEP2) each agent is put in a simulator according to his coordinates given in STEP1.
 STEP3) each agent turns in the direction of his destination given in STEP1.
 STEP5) check the conditions of cells around his destination, and if the conditions have changed, change his destination, if not do nothing.

STEP6) advance a step.
 STEP7) avoid obstacles.
 STEP8) repeat from STEP5 to STEP7 until arriving at his destination.

6-3 BEHAVIORAL SIMULATIONS BASED ON THE TRANSITION RULES

Based on models above, the simulator is made and is launched. Purposes of the simulation are as below.

- i) To see how the simulator works.
- ii) To see how the transition rules work.
- iii) To propose a design method from the analysis of results.

1) RIPLEY’S L-FUNCTION FOR AGENT PATTERN ANALYSIS

The disposition of agents in the simulator is analyzed using L-function, which is based on K-function method (Ripley 1976, 1977)⁽¹¹⁾⁽¹²⁾;

$$K(r) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{2\pi r}{w_{i,t}} (d_{i,j}) \quad (\text{equation1})$$

, where λ is corresponding to density of cells ($=n/A$; n : number of points of area A , A : area of the site). $w_{i,j}$ is a the circumference of radius r , centered on an arbitrary point p_i , intersected with the study area (equation1).

L-function (equation2) (Ripley, 1979) is defined based on K-function above;¹³⁾

$$L(r) = \sqrt{\frac{K(r)}{2\pi}} - d \quad (\text{equation2})$$

When $L(r)=0$ for all r , the disposition is the complete random pattern. When $L(r) > 0$ indicates clustering of the disposition and the attraction among points, and when $L(r) < 0$ indicates the regularity of the disposition and the repulsion among points.

2) INITIAL CONDITION 1: STUDY ABOUT THE PRIORITY ORDER

To see how the priority of order works, simulations are executed. The simulator stops at 200 steps.

- (a) Number of agents
60 agents are created step by step (1 agent/step) and move in the simulator.
- (b) Priority order of agents

Table8 shows the number of cells for each priority order. For example, in simulation1, there are 30

cells which have the order “123”, and the other 30 cells have the order “132”.

(c) Rate of friends

Agents choose one “friend number” between 1 and 5 at random (rate of friends is 1/5).

(d) Social distance, Personal distance

Social distances of agents are evenly 12 cells (=3m).

Personal distances of agents are evenly 4 cells (=1m).

Table8 Partition of cells

priority order	123	132	213	231	312	321
simulation1	30	30	0	0	0	0
simulation2	0	0	30	30	0	0
simulation3	0	0	0	0	30	30
simulation4	10	10	10	10	10	10

3) SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation results are below (fig.27).

Fig.27 Simulation results

Fig.28 shows the values L(r) of 4 dispositions. All the 4 L(r)s have the greatest point around r=3. The greatest point comes before at the number of cells of the personal distance (=4 cells). From L(t) of simulation3, (“away from others” is strong) its disposition is dispersed the most among 4 simulations. All L(r)s become 0 at about 20, and they become less

than 0. When L(r)s are more than 0, simulation2 (“prefer around trees”) is the most clustered, and is followed by simulation1 (“beside friends”), simulation4. When it is hot, the situation is similar to simulation2.

Fig28. L(r) of 4 simulations

4) INITIAL CONDITION 2: STUDY ABOUT AGENT’S VARIABLES AND DISPOSITION OF TREES

To see how variables work in simulator, simulations are executed. The simulator stops at 200 steps.

(a) Disposition of trees

3 dispositions of trees are tested (fig.29). One is an actual disposition (68 cells of trees), 2 dispositions are arranged from the 68 tree cells.

Fig.29 Dispositions of cells Left:actual disposition, center: disposition “a”, right: disposition “b”

(b) Number of agents

60 agents are created step by step (1 agent/step) and move in the simulator.

(c) Priority order of cells

Agents’ priority of order is the same with that of simulation4 on table7.

(d) Rate of friends

Agents choose one “friend number” between 1 and 5 at random (rate of friends is 1/5) or between 1 and 10 at random (rate of friends is 1/10).

(e) Social distance, Personal distance

Social distances of agents are evenly 12 cells (=3m) or are evenly 30 cells (7.5m).

5) SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation results are below (Table9).

Fig.30 shows the values $L(r)$ of 12 dispositions.

(a) Actual Disposition

Before at around $r=20$, all the dispositions are estimated to be clustered. The greatest values vary according to social distance (S_d in the graph), and when the social distance is 30, dispositions are more clustered.

(b) Disposition a

Values of $L(r)$ don't show a big difference according to variables. From the values after at around $r=20$, when the social distance is 12, the dispositions are more repulsive than that of 30.

(c) Disposition b

Values of $L(r)$ vary according to variables. Disposition is clustered more when social distance is 30 than when that of 12, and this doesn't depends on the

number of friends.

(d) All the dispositions

All the dispositions relatively disperse when friends are not many (1/10) and social distance is 12. When the social distance is little, some agents cannot find trees and friends, that's why agents disperse.

7. PROPOSITION OF A DESIGN METHOD

(a) ABOUT USERS

From the simulations, variables of agents affect a lot to their disposition. When designing, it is essential to consider the character of users. The number of friends can be used to consider if the place is private or public in the real space, for example.

(b) ABOUT ELEMENTS ITSELF

As a tree affects some human behaviors, people need some particular environmental quality. So when we design, it is necessary to foresee what quality

Fig.30 $L(r)$ values of all 12 simulations. Left: $L(r)$ of actual disposition, Center: $L(r)$ of disposition "a", Left: $L(r)$ of disposition "b"

Table9 Spatial dispositions of the simulator as results of simulation

	actual disposition		disposition a		disposition b	
	social distance = 12	social distance = 30	social distance = 12	social distance = 30	social distance = 12	social distance = 30
friends : 1/5						
friends : 1/10						

possible human behaviors need. The simulator shows examples of variables which need to be considered when designing. The disposition of trees and the social distance relate to dispositions of agents. That is to say, it is necessary to consider the disposition of attractive points and the visibility of the site at the same time, for example.

(c) ABOUT RELATIONS BETWEEN ELEMENTS

As the simulator shows, dispositions of attractive cells affect a lot to agents' disposition. We can say this for the real space. As well as the quality of the environment, the disposition of architectural elements can make people's stops longer and frequent. Appropriate dispositions of architectural elements will make the impacts of the design much stronger.

(d) ABOUT STRUCTURES OF ELEMENTS

This study also shows an impact to habitual tendency of human behaviors in the site. The campus square gives many habitudes like what we can see students' typical behaviors in the site. So this study also shows the importance to consider the structure of the site. A few habitual environment was simulated this time (e.g. total number of friends etc.), but we can simulate another situation by the simulator.

8. CONCLUSION

A basic method for analyzing the human behaviors in a daily situation is constructed, and this multiagent-based simulator can be used to test other interrelations between the human behavior and the architectural/urban space. The architectural/urban space is a complex system composed of infinite architectural elements. This system depends not only on the movements of each element but also on their interrelations. It is necessary to design architectural space according to the interrelation among the entities, not according to one architectural vision only.

REFERENCES

- 1) Susan Petrilli: *From pragmatic philosophy to behavioral semiotics*, *Semiotica*, Volume 2004, Issue 148, Pages 277-315.
- 2) Japan Meteorological Agency, 2010.10.20., <http://www.data.jma.go.jp/>, (referenced 2010.11.16.)
- 3) Hitoshi Watanabe: *Shinken-chikugakutaiki*, vol.11, Ecological psychology, Shokoku sya, pp153-234, 1982.
- 4) Burks, A. (ed.): *Collected Papers of C.S. Peirce Vol.8*, The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 1979.
- 5) Claus Dreyer: *DIE REPERTOIRES DER ARCHITECTURE UNTER SMIOTISCHEM GESICHTSPUNKT*, *Semiosis* 19, Heft 3, Baden-Baden: Agis-verlag, pp.37-48, 1980.
- 6) Hall, E.: *Proxemics*, *Current Anthropology*, Vol.9, No.2/3, pp.92-93, 1963.
- 7) Hall, E.: *A System for the Notation of Proxemic Behavior*, *American Anthropologist New Series*, Vol.65, No.5, 1963.
- 8) Von Neumann J.: *Theory of Self-Reproducing Automata*, (edit., Burks, A.), University of Illinois, Urbana IL., 1966.
- 9) Shin Morita, Hideomi Yamamoto, et al.: *Simulation of Purchase in a Store by Cellular Automata*, Transactions of JSCES, Paper NO.19990019, pp.2, 1999.
- 10) Artisoc academic: Multi-agent-based simulator, Kozokeikaku Kenkyusyo
- 11) Ripley, B.D.: *The second-order analysis of stationary point processes*, *Journal of Applied Probability*, 13, 255-66., 1976.
- 12) Ripley, B.D.: *Modeling spatial patterns*, *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series B* 39, 172-192., 1977.
- 13) Ripley, B.D.: *Tests of 'randomness' for spatial point patterns*, *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series B* 41, 368-374., 1979.

NOTES

1) Peirce's semiotic explains not only the linguistic phenomena but all the phenomena. Peirce classifies all the phenomena into the following three categories;

"Firstness is the mode of being of that which is such as it is, positively and without reference to anything else.

Secondness is the mode of being of that which is such as it is, with respect to a second but regardless of any third.

Thirdness is the mode of being of that which is such as it is, in bringing a second and third into relation to each other."(CP 8.328*, 1904)

In this study, according to these categories, we understand the human behavior as the interactive process among three elements such as the object of human behavior, the environment, and the human interpretation (including feeling, action and thought etc.).

*CP x,y: CP= "*Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce*, x=Volume, y=Paragraph

2) Peirce's three categories are applied in semiotics of architecture as by Kiefer (1970), Dreyer (1979), Arin (1981). Winfried Noth: *Handbook of semiotics (Advances in Semiotics)*, Indiana University Press, p438.

※This work is supported by Grants-in-Aid for Scientific Research "Design Theory for Dynamical Systems with Semiosis" by Tetsuo Sawaragi et al., 2007-2011, and for JSPS Fellows (No. 023 · 3917).